

EFFECT OF REINFORCING PARTICLES ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN A METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

F. Ellyin and Chingshen Li
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Alberta
Edmonton, Canada, T6G 2G8

ABSTRACT

The effect of reinforcing particles on fatigue crack growth in $Al_2O_3/6061$ Al composite, is found to depend on the crack length and the applied stress levels. Reinforcing particles retard short crack growth considerably unless the maximum cyclic stress is near the fracture stress of the material. Near threshold stress intensity levels, the resistance of the material to long fatigue crack growth increases with the volume fraction of particles. In the intermediate stress intensity range the particles have little influence on the long fatigue crack growth. An energy based analysis is conducted to rationalize the inability of particles to resist long crack growth in the intermediate ΔK values.

INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that in particulate reinforced metal matrix composites(PMMC) cracks with longer length display micro-structure sensitivity than in metals and alloys[1]. Measured threshold stress intensity levels for long crack growth in SiC particulate-reinforced aluminum alloy composites are a function of particle volume fraction and particle size[2]. In contrast, in the intermediate stress intensity range, the reinforced SiC particles do not appear to affect the long crack growth in the composite[2]. These results suggest that the particle's effect on fatigue crack growth in the PMMCs depends on both particle size and volume fraction, and the applied stress.

The purpose of this paper is to provide an understanding of the effect of reinforcing particles on both the short and long crack growth in the $Al_2O_3/6061$ aluminum alloy composite under different applied stress ranges and stress intensity factors.

MATERIALS and EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material in this investigation is a 6061 aluminum alloy composite reinforced with 10 μ m-average size Al_2O_3 particles with 10%(W10) and 20%(W20) particle volume fraction. The yield

stress for W10 and W20 at T6 condition is, respectively, 276MPa and 352 MPa. Based on the manufacture's data for a series of composites with different particle volume fraction, the yield stress, σ_{yc} , of a composite is a function of the yield stress of the same alloy comprising the matrix, σ_{ya} , and volume fraction of particles, f_v :

$$\sigma_{yc} = \sigma_{ya}(1 + f_v)^\alpha / C \quad (1)$$

in which α and C are constants and are found to be equal to 2.1 and 1.14, respectively, for the Al_2O_3 particulate-reinforced 6061 aluminum alloy composites.

The procedures used to induce a short fatigue crack trigger are described in reference[1]. Fatigue crack propagation tests were subsequently performed under tension-compression cyclic loading at a constant load ratio, $R=-0.4$, with a frequency of 5 Hz, at room temperature. The crack length was periodically measured using the replica method.

RESULTS

LONG CRACK GROWTH AT INTERMEDIATE STRESS INTENSITY

The propagation rates of cracks longer than 3 mm in both W10 and W20 composites as well as in 6061 alloy are displayed in Fig. 1 as a function of the nominal stress-intensity range in a log-log scale. In the intermediate stress-intensity range, all the data locate in a narrow band surrounding a straight line. This range can be approximately represented by:

$$da/dN = c(\Delta K)^{3.3} \quad (2)$$

This overlapping of the growth rate curve for the two composites with different particle volume fraction and the alloy indicates that the long crack growth rate is particle-independent.

Fig. 1 Variation of the crack growth rate in terms of the maximum stress intensity, K_{max} , for 20% and 10% Al_2O_3 /6061 composites and 6061 aluminum alloy with $R=-0.4$.

NEAR THRESHOLD LONG CRACK GROWTH

As shown in Fig. 1, the threshold stress intensity factor is $7.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ for W20 composite, $5.0 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ for W10 composite and $4.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ for the 6061 alloy. Hence, the material resistance to the initial long crack growth increases with the particle volume fraction. Note that ΔK_{th} of W20 composite is slightly higher than W10 composite, but much higher than the alloy. Shang and Ritchie[2] have observed a considerable increase in ΔK_{th} with the increased particle size, but a slight increase with the volume fraction in SiC reinforced composite.

SHORT CRACK GROWTH

Figure 2 displays the growth rate of a short crack, $310 \mu\text{m}$ in length, under the intermediate stress range, $\sigma_{max}=110 \text{ MPa}$. It is seen that both growth direction and growth rate of short cracks in the particulate-reinforced composites are dramatically affected by the particles, especially by the larger particles. Moreover, the length range of short cracks displaying microstructure-sensitivity in the composites is much larger than in metals and alloys. In the above stress range, fracture and debonding of particles are prominent and these play a key role in maintaining the crack growth.

PRE-CEASE SHORT CRACK GROWTH AT CYCLIC STRESS BELOW THE FATIGUE LIMIT

Pre-cess short crack growth has been identified in the composite[1]. It was observed that these short cracks grow in an uneven manner before they cease to propagate at the cyclic stress amplitude below the fatigue limit of this material. Figure 3 shows a typical tortuous growth pattern of a pre-cess short crack near a cluster of particles at a maximum cyclic stress of 99 MPa . The drastically varied growth rate of this short crack versus the projected crack length is plotted in Fig. 3b. The growth rate drops dramatically as the short crack tends to change its direction. The crack propagates along the slip lines and deflects to avoid the nearby particles. As the crack front grows closer to the large particle blocking its path, the crack ceases to propagate. It is interesting to note that few particles of average size are fractured or debonded in this stress range. Therefore, the fatigue limit seems to be a threshold for short crack growth, below which the cyclic plasticity ahead of a short crack can develop, but it can not induce high enough stress to break the nearby particles.

AN ENERGY ANALYSIS ON PARTICLE-INDEPENDENCY OF LONG CRACKS

It is significant that all the three crack growth rate curves converge in the intermediate range of ΔK as shown in Fig. 1. This points out to the inability of reinforcing particles to resist the fatigue crack growth in this region. Similar phenomena have been noted in several other PMMCs[2].

The fatigue crack growth behaviour in metallic materials is determined by the crack tip-plasticity[4]. The single slip band ahead of a long crack occurs under near-threshold stress intensity and a multiple slip plastic zone is observed at the intermediate intensity factor range.

An energy analysis is developed for the long crack growth in the PMMC under intermediate range of ΔK . Figure 4 b and c display the plastic zone ahead of a crack in the composite and a much larger plastic zone ahead of the same length crack in the same alloy as the matrix under the same applied ΔK .

Fig.2 Short crack path and its growth rate against crack length under $\sigma_{max}=110$ MPa with $R=-0.4$.

The first law of thermodynamics applied to the fatigue crack propagation requires that the work per cycle to be equal to the dissipated heat[5]. This leads to

$$da/dN = A\Delta K^4 / (\mu\sigma_y 2U) \tag{3}$$

where U is an effective surface energy, σ_y is the cyclic yielding stress and μ is the shear modulus of the material. As a crack propagates in this range, most particles on the crack path are fractured. On a unit length area created by the crack advance in the metal matrix composite, the area fraction f_A of fractured particles equals to $f_v^{2/3}$. The effective surface energy is given by

$$U_c = U_m(1-f_A) + U_p f_A \tag{4}$$

where U_m and U_p are effective surface energy of matrix and particles, respectively. Since there is no plastic deformation at the ceramic particles, U_p is much smaller than U_m and is neglected in the following calculation. The long crack growth rate(3) in the composite can be written as

$$(da/dN)_c = A\Delta K^4 / (\mu_c \sigma_{yc} 2U_c) \tag{5}$$

Substitution of eqns (1) and (4) into (5) yields

$$(da/dN)_c = A\Delta K^4 / (\mu_c \sigma_{yc} 2U_m) [(1+f)^\alpha (1-f^{2/3})/C] \tag{6}$$

Fig. 3 Pre-cess short crack growth path and crack growth rate under $\sigma_{\max}=99\text{MPa}$ with $R=0.37$.

A comparison of $(da/dN)_c$ with the crack growth rate of the same length crack in the alloy $(da/dN)_a$ under the same ΔK leads to

$$(da/dN)_c / (da/dN)_a = 1.14 \mu_a / \mu_c (1 + f_v)^\alpha (1 - f_v^{2/3}) \quad (7)$$

Since the right-hand term in the above equation is approximately equal to 1, the growth rate in the composite $(da/dN)_c$ approaches to the crack growth rate in the alloy $(da/dN)_a$. The above analysis shows that the decrease of the input work due to the reduced plastic zone by reinforced particles is balanced by the particle-reduced effective surface energy.

Fig. 4 Schematic illustration of cyclic plastic zones of long cracks: a) in PMMC under near threshold stress intensity; b) in PMMC under intermediate stress intensity; c) in the same alloy with the composite matrix under the same stress intensity as b).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The reinforcing Al_2O_3 particles in 6061 aluminum alloy composites enhance the material's resistance to the short crack growth and near threshold-long crack growth. The measured threshold stress-intensity levels for the composite with 20% volume fraction particles is higher than that with 10% particles.
2. Drastically varied growth rate and direction of the short cracks and pre-cess short cracks, are due to the local, individual particle's effect on the extension of the crack tip cyclic plasticity.
3. A common characteristic of particulate-reinforced composites is that the long crack growth rate is independent of the reinforcing particles in the intermediate range of ΔK . This observation is rationalized based on an energy analysis.
4. Both thresholds for long fatigue crack growth (ΔK_{th}) and short crack growth (fatigue limit, σ_n) refer to a common critical loading condition above which the crack tip cyclic plastic zone is able to extend across the average-size particles.

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